

Why do we do what we do?

Digital Preservation Coalition
Poster by Karyn Williamson

We're keeping knowledge alive for students, scholars, and our community into the future.
Student and Scholarly Services,
The University of Melbourne

...moments of connection across time and space

Irina Schidt - American University Cairo

When records are lost, blurred or inaccessible, residents and citizens lose their right to know how decisions were made and how public money was spent

Villy Magero

The emergence of libraries and archives stems from humanity's need to preserve cultural heritage. Their core mission is to collect, organize, preserve, and distribute the memories of human civilization.

Zhenxin Wu- NDPP National Library of China

...we preserve for future use

Helen Dafter - The Postal Museum

...public access to information... is an important cornerstone of democracy

Kommunalförbundet Sydarkivera

Why Preserve?

Preservation is no longer just about storing files. It's about shaping identity, protecting truth, and creating pathways for innovation

Holly Duncan - Preferred media

Find out more

Tell us your why

#WDPD2025

#WhyPreserve

A new advocacy campaign for the sector by the sector